

EFFECT OF SEA WATER CONFINEMENT ON CYCLIC FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF MARINE COMPOSITES

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Abstract

This study focuses on the effect of complete water immersion and one sided water exposure condition on the cyclic fatigue behavior of carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester composites (CF/VE) that use as facings for sandwich structures whose mechanical behavior is influenced by resin, for example $[\pm 45]_{2s}$. In our study, experimental results for facings resulted in failures for much lower number of loading cycles when fatigued under immersed conditions surrounded by sea water than in air. Once fluid has penetrated the composite surface by capillary action through micro-cracks or along the sides through inter-layers/laminates, its inability to evacuate the water that has entered the composite and the large compressive stress it experiences during the down loading stages of the fatigue load due to the near incompressibility of water results in a large increased of internal pore/crack fluid pressure dominating the failure mechanism. Sea water induced fatigue degradation data and corresponding micro-structure after failure using high resolution X-ray computed tomography are presented.

1 Introduction

The failure of CF/VE composites under fatigue loading results from accumulated damage as a result of various deformation mechanisms including fiber delamination, matrix failure, and fiber failure. Additionally, for naval composites, marine environment such as sea water exposure influence the fiber, matrix and the fiber/matrix interface most often simultaneously. In addition, they encounter different loading patterns during their operational life due to sea water surrounding the composites during their service life.

Extensive studies [1-3] have shown that fatigue loading is important to consider for evaluating

critical modes of structural failures. Fatigue damage as a function of modulus degradation was first proposed for predicting fatigue life [4]. A stiffness degradation model was used to predict the fatigue life of fiber and matrix dominated graphite/epoxy composites [5, 6].

Recent studies of authors [7, 8] using carbon fiber-reinforced vinyl ester composites with a lay-up configuration of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ exhibited disparate failure mechanisms when fatigued in air as compared to immersed conditions under sea water, resulting in premature failures when completely submerged in fluid. These studies focused on the effect of confined or immersed and one sided water exposure on the cyclic fatigue behavior of resin dominated CF/VE facings used in marine sandwich structures.

2 Material

The facing material was made of carbon stitch bonded fabric designated by LT650- C10-R2VE supplied by the Devold AMT AS, Sweden. This was an equibiaxial fabric produced using Toray's T700 12k carbon fiber tow with a vinyl ester compatible sizing. The matrix used was Dow Chemical's DERAKANE 510A-40, a brominated vinyl ester, formulated for the VARTM process. The bromination imparts a fire-resistant property to the composite. Carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester laminated composites consisting of fiber dominated $[0/90]_{2s}$ and matrix-dominated $[15/75]_{2s}$, $[30/60]_{2s}$, $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ cross-stitched lay-ups are considered in this study. Test materials were fabricated at North Carolina A&T University following standard VARTM protocol and appropriate post-curing conditions [9].

3 Material and Experimental approach

3.1 Material preparation

Various types of samples including dry and saturated in sea water were considered for the study. The wet condition (saturated sample) was achieved by immersing the carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester samples in a bath of sea water at 40 °C for at least 6 months prior to testing. Generally saturation upon immersion was achieved within approximately three months, with a weight gain of about 0.4 %. CF/VE laminated composites consisting of $[0/90]_{2S}$, $[15/75]_{2S}$, $[30/60]_{2S}$, and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ cross-stitched layups were prepared as shown in Fig. 1 for this study.

Fig. 1 A carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester (CF/VE) composites panel prepared at different orientations with final dimension sample of 200mm by 25mm consisting of four cross-stitch plies of Devold LT 650 (12k Toray's Torayca T700 carbon fiber tow) and vinyl ester resin. The structure of each stitch bonded carbon fabric ply combines the fill face in 0° direction and warp face in 90° direction stitched with a polyester knitting thread used to form the panel of $[\text{fill face/warp face}]_{2S}$.

3.2 Static test

A 250 kN 810 MTS mechanical testing system was employed with an MTS 609 alignment fixture to integrate a smaller 50 kN axial force transducer for precise axial force measurements. Rectangular CF/VE samples which are 200 mm long, 25 mm wide and approximately 2.5 mm thick were used for mechanical testing as per ASTM D3039 procedures [10]. Fig. 2 shows an optical image of a sample. Tensile tests were performed to determine the Young's modulus, E , along different orientations of

CF/VE layups under strain control at rate of 300 $\mu\epsilon/\text{min}$ and for a maximum tensile strain of 750 $\mu\epsilon$, which is well within the linear elastic axial strain limit prior to inelastic strains. Failure strength test was also performed using the same equipment and procedure. Strains were recorded by an extensometer. Tabs were mounted at the ends of the specimens using West System 105/205 epoxy and epoxy hardener, in order to direct failure away from the stress concentrations at the gripped portions. Prior to the tensile tests, all the specimens were completely dried at ambient temperature in desiccators.

Fig. 2 Carbon fiber/vinyl ester (CF/VE) sample with final dimension of 200 mm by 25 mm consists of 12k Toray's T700 carbon fiber tow and vinyl ester resin.

3.3 Fatigue test

The tension-tension cyclic fatigue behavior of the composites were obtained in general accordance with test procedures described in ASTM D 3479/D 3479M standards [11]. The cyclic load was applied in a servo-hydraulic test machine at frequency of 1 Hz with an R-ratio $\left(\frac{\sigma_{min}}{\sigma_{max}}\right)$ of 0.2 with $\sigma_{max} = 2/3\sigma_{failure}$ MPa. All matrix-dominated specimens were subjected to in-plane tensile cyclic loading at axial stress corresponding to 2/3 of ultimate strength. Two to six replicate samples were tested in each of the four following conditions 1) dry samples tested in air, 2) saturated samples tested in air, 3) dry samples tested while immersed in sea water, 4) saturated samples tested while immersed in sea water, 5) dry samples tested while only one side (surface) was exposed to sea water, and 6) saturated samples tested while one surface was exposed sea water to simulate material used for the outside ship structure in contact with water.

Fig. 3 shows the dimensions of the specimen as well as the water-filled latex membrane attached to the central region of the sample while subjected to tension-tension fatigue load cycles using a servo-hydraulic testing system.

Fig. 3 Carbon fiber vinyl/ester composite specimen (CF/VE) with an attached latex membrane system that maintains given water exposure condition during fatigue loading cycles.

To simulate the immersed condition in sea environment, the cyclic loading was applied with water surrounding the sample undergoing cyclic loading using a thin impermeable latex membrane. Under tension-tension cyclic fatigue test, orientation dependence of CF/VE samples exhibit disparate failure mechanisms depending on access to sea water while they are subjected to cyclic stress.

In this study secant and tangent modulus, E_s and E_t as a function of loading cycle (Fig. 4) are used to track degradation due to sea water confinement for a given lay-up orientation.

Fig. 4. Secant and Tangent Modulus used in this study

$$E_s = \frac{\sigma_{total}}{\epsilon_{total}} \text{ and } E_t = \frac{\sigma_{total}}{\epsilon_n} \quad (1)$$

4 Results and discussions

The Young's modulus E and failure stress of layups at different orientations, $[0/90]_{2S}$, $[15/75]_{2S}$, $[30/60]_{2S}$, and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$, were evaluated for varying loading cycles during tension-tension fatigue tests. The average elastic moduli and ultimate strength at different orientations at dry and wet state are shown in Table 1. The stress at failure as a function of orientation was then used as the basis in determining tension-tension fatigue loads as shown in Table 2.

CF/VE facing orientation	Moduli (GPa)		Stress at failure (MPa)	
	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
$[0/90]_{2S}$	49.7	48.9	975	
$[15/75]_{2S}$	36.1	36.5	235.3	237.5
$[30/60]_{2S}$	22.6	21.1	154.9	150.8
$[\pm 45]_{2S}$	17.3	16.2	132.3	125.2

Table 1: Summary of moduli and failure stresses at different orientations

Sample orientation	σ_{max} (MPa)	σ_{mean} (MPa)
$[0/90]_{2S}$	800	480
$[15/75]_{2S}$	156	94
$[30/60]_{2S}$	100	60
$[\pm 45]_{2S}$	76	46

Table 2: Stress levels for cyclic loading of $[0/90]_{2S}$, $[15/75]_{2S}$, $[30/60]_{2S}$, and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ specimens

In our past study [12, 13], a comparative study on the effects of sea water on failure stress was evaluated using at least three dry and wet facing specimens obtained from the same region in a panel. Fig. 5 shows that $\sigma_{failure}$ of $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ layup decreases

by 5% due to sea water effect and $[30/60]_{2S}$ facing resulted in a 2.5% reduction due to sea water effect. However, no difference due to sea water was found on the failure state of stress for $[15/75]_{2S}$ facing orientation, consistent with expectation that matrix dominated properties are mostly impacted by sea environment degradation. As a result, only resin-dominated sample observations are presented for this tension-tension cyclic fatigue behavior.

Fig. 5 Reduction in tensile failure stress due to sea water exposure at different orientations.

Experimental results for resin-dominated facings yielded failures under much lower number of cycles when fatigued under immersed conditions surrounded by sea water than in air. Once fluid has penetrated the test samples by capillary action through micro-cracks, matrix-fiber bundle interface, or inter-layers, its inability to evacuate the ingress water sample during the down loading portion of the fatigue cycle and the near incompressibility of impregnated water results in large internal pressure leading to premature failure with rapid accumulation of damage for matrix dominated samples. It was observed that sea water confinement during fatigue loading did not significantly reduce fatigue life for samples oriented such that the mechanical behavior was fiber bundle dominated as seen in Fig. 6. However, it is noted that the sea water confinement significantly reduced fatigue life on resin dominated samples, for example $[\pm 45]_{2S}$, at the same stress level of $2/3\sigma_{failure}$. As can be inferred from Fig. 6, the degradation of the tangent modulus with accumulated cycles can be clearly seen in the resin load-bearing sample but not in the fiber dominated sample.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the tangent modulus vs. the percent of fatigue life for fiber dominated $[0/90]_{2S}$ and matrix dominated $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ samples in air and confined conditions.

The fatigue life of composites corresponds to the number of load cycles to failure. The tension-tension fatigue data for different conditions was normalized for comparison purpose using percentage of fatigue life, which is the ratio of “number of load cycles” to “total number of load cycles to failure” as seen in Figs Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

Fig. 7 shows the comparison from a dry matrix-dominated sample in air, wet immersed and one sided wet immersed sample. It was noted the true strain data prior to failure was much lower in wet immersed cases compared to dry sample in air. It also shows that wet one side water exposed sample shows corresponding and expected differences when compared with dry sample in air and wet sample completely immersed in sea water. Quantitatively, a 50% degradation of tangent modulus corresponded to failure in fatigue for matrix-dominated samples $[15/75]_{2S}$, $[30/60]_{2S}$, and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ as shown in Fig. 8. It shows the data comparison for samples at different orientations without water confinement.

As shown in Fig. 9 with water confinement effects, it shows that the number of cycles to failure reduced considerably when compared to dry condition in air. Note that the tensile strain data prior to failure also showed a similar degradation effect for all resin-dominated composites due to sea water confinement.

Fig. 7. Tangent modulus reduction vs Fatigue life of $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ for different testing conditions

Fig. 8. Tangent modulus degradation for dry $[15/75]_{2S}$, $[30/60]_{2S}$, and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ specimens tested in air.

Fig. 9 Number of cycles to failure vs testing conditions for $[15/75]_{2S}$, $[30/60]_{2S}$, $[\pm 45]_{2S}$

Relative percentage of degradation of matrix-dominated CF/VE composites at various orientations compared to dry condition in air is shown in Table 2.

Sample Condition	Cyclic Fatigue Degradation of matrix-dominated composites (%)
Dry in air	ref
Dry immersed	~70 %
Dry one side immersed	~40 %

Table 3: Summary of experimental results

Similarly experimental results for dry and wet $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminates of CF/VE composites yielded failures under much fewer numbers of cycles, a drop of up to 80% in the number of cycles to failure, when fatigued under completely immersed conditions than in air. Also when fatigued with the conditions of water confinement such that only one side or face is exposed to water, they failed at far fewer loading cycles, approximately 50 % less of loading cycles compared to the samples with no water confinement (i.e., in air) as shown in Fig. 10. It shows the comparison between dry in air and confined or one sided water exposure while testing on $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ samples. Further reductions of fatigue life were observed when CF/VE composites were exposure to the sea water.

Fig. 10 Fatigue life loss comparison of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ due to sea water exposure in marine environment

It was observed that the damage evolution during cyclic fatigue in matrix dominated samples is from a combination of the coalesced matrix cracks parallel to the fiber and delaminations. Additionally, voids between matrix/fiber rapidly grow and lead to the early fatigue failure mode when confined in sea water. High resolution micro-tomography experiments were performed on failed samples ex-situ to understand the modes failure and related differences for two conditions. Fig. 11 shows an example result which indicates that sample fatigued under sea water confinement failed from delaminations and the mechanism is that water enters resin cracks and quickly increases local stresses due to its incompressibility under cyclic loading leading to cascading effect on crack growth from outer layers resulting in large delaminations (Fig. 11). As seen in Fig. 12, the samples fatigued in air indicate that all four layers of carbon fiber participated effectively in load transfer prior to sudden failure.

Fig. 11 X-ray tomography data showing causes of reduction in fatigue life due to water confinement.

Fig. 12 X-ray tomography data showing causes of fatigue failure without water confinement effect.

5 Concluding remarks

It was shown in this work that the fatigue life of matrix-dominated polymeric composites shortened dramatically, up to 85%, when cyclic loading was applied under fully confined immersed conditions. A very significant loss of mechanical strength under cyclic loading due to sea water exposure was found while the stress cycles were applied. The results obtained for water confined samples with exposed edges, simulates the worst case exposure conditions for marine structures. Only one face of composite panel is actually exposed to sea water. However, as shown in this paper, even one sided exposure to sea water also leads to considerable reduction in the fatigue life, approximately 40% on matrix-dominated composites, $[15/75]_{2S}$, $[30/60]_{2S}$, and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$. Therefore, water confinement or exposure, while cyclic or dynamic loading is applied, plays an important role on the cyclic fatigue behavior of CF/VE composites used in marine applications. It is confirmed from the micro-structure data using high resolution x-ray tomography that water availability during cyclic fatigue initiate ingress, followed by large internal fluids leading to observed reductions in fatigue life for matrix-dominated composite layups. Therefore, sea water degradation due to coupled effects with cyclic stress should be considered for naval structures.

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